

METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN ACADEMIC LYCEUMS

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada akademik ta'limda raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida ingliz tilini o'qitish usullari yoritilgan. Maqola mazmuni "Environmental problems and True, False, Not Given questions in Reading" mavzusida o'tkazilgan ochiq dars tahliliga asoslanadi. Unda dars jarayonida elektron doska, slyaydlar, interfaol o'yinlar hamda guruhli ishlash metodlaridan foydalanish orqali o'quvchilarning bilim va ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish masalalari ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli texnologiyalar, ingliz tilini o'qitish, interfaol metodlar, elektron doska, slyaydlar, guruhli ishlash, True/False/Not Given, reading ko'nikmalari, IELTS, CEFR, role play

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются методы преподавания английского языка с использованием цифровых технологий в академическом образовании. Содержание статьи основано на анализе открытого урока по теме «Экологические проблемы и вопросы типа «Верно/Неверно/Не указано» в чтении». Рассматриваются вопросы развития знаний и навыков учащихся посредством использования электронных досок, слайдов, интерактивных игр и методов групповой работы в процессе урока.

Ключевые слова: цифровые технологии, преподавание английского языка, интерактивные методы, электронные доски, слайды, групповая работа, вопросы типа «Верно/Неверно/Не указано», навыки чтения, IELTS, CEFR, ролевая игра

Abstract. This article examines methods of teaching English using digital technologies in academic education. The article is based on the analysis of an open lesson on the topic "Environmental Issues and True/False/Not Stated Questions in Reading." It examines the development of students' knowledge and skills through the use of electronic whiteboards, slides, interactive games, and group work methods during the lesson.

Keywords: digital technologies, English language teaching, interactive methods, electronic whiteboards, slides, group work, True/False/Not Stated questions, reading skills, IELTS, CEFR, role-play.

Introduction

A number of resolutions and decrees adopted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev clearly define the tasks of improving the quality of foreign language teaching, widely introducing modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies into the educational process. In particular, Resolution No. PQ-1875 emphasizes the need to radically improve the system of teaching foreign languages, improve the qualifications of teachers, and create modern educational and methodological support. Resolution No. PQ-5117 also identifies the popularization of foreign language learning, increasing young people's interest in language learning, and organizing education based on modern digital technologies as priority

tasks. Based on these resolutions, widespread use of multimedia tools, electronic boards, online platforms, and interactive methods is being introduced in educational institutions. As a result of these reforms, there has been a need to abandon traditional methods in teaching English and switch to innovative approaches. In particular, it is important to organize lessons aimed at developing students' competencies such as independent thinking, analysis, and logical conclusions. This article analyzes an open lesson on the topic "Environmental problems and True, False, Not Given questions in Reading" conducted by an English teacher based on the above decisions and modern requirements. The use of digital technologies, interactive methods, and approaches aimed at developing students' knowledge and skills during the lesson are scientifically and practically covered.

The relevance of this study is that it analyzes the methodological foundations and pedagogical effectiveness of using modern software tools in teaching the subject of impulse in academic lyceums.

The lesson on the topic “Environmental problems and True, False, Not Given questions in Reading” was organized on the basis of modern pedagogical approaches, and digital technologies and interactive methods were effectively used. This approach served to develop not only theoretical knowledge, but also practical skills of students. At the beginning of the lesson, the students were focused and divided into two groups - “Diamonds” and “Leaders”. An atmosphere of healthy competition was created between the groups, which increased the activity of students in the lesson. During the review of the topics covered, students' knowledge was activated through quick questions and answers, brainstorming, and the “Jeopardy” game organized on the electronic board. This process was more interesting and effective due to the fact that it was organized using digital technologies. Electronic boards, slides, and visual materials were widely used to explain the new topic. In particular, within the framework of the topic “Environmental problems”, information about global environmental problems was presented visually. This helped students to understand the topic more deeply. At the same time, the content of the True, False, Not Given question types, their criteria for distinguishing them, and the techniques for solving them were explained step by step. The teacher paid special attention to the following aspects as the technique for completing the questions: reading the question carefully, identifying key words from the text, finding synonyms and paraphrases, and analyzing the correspondence between the text and the question. Through the examples provided, students practically learned to distinguish between True (corresponds), False (does not correspond), and Not Given (no information is given). Reinforcement In the second stage, students worked in groups. As each group worked on the assigned tasks, they discussed and corrected mistakes together. This developed the students' skills of working together, critical thinking, and justifying their opinions.

The use of the role play method was also of particular importance during the lesson. By staging environmental problems, students not only understood the topic more deeply, but also had the opportunity to communicate freely in English, express their opinions, and develop their speaking skills. Also, through speaking tasks, students were given the task of preparing a 30-second speech on various topics. This method served to develop their independent thinking, quick response ability, and oral speech. The digital technologies used during the lesson — electronic whiteboards, slides, and computer tools — increased the effectiveness of education. Interactive methods ensured the active participation of students in the lesson. As a result, students deeply mastered the topic and acquired practical skills in correctly analyzing True,

False, and Not Given questions. In general, the harmonious use of digital technologies and interactive methods in this lesson provided high efficiency in developing students' knowledge, skills and competencies. And in this lesson, students mainly learned how to find the right answers to the most common questions in the IELTS and CEFR exams and how to distinguish them from each other. These types of questions make many young people think about much higher exams. In addition, the current global problems, especially air pollution, global warming and plastic pollution, were discussed and effective methods were given to solve them. The students were also informed about the benefits of reducing the use of single-use plastic items in daily life. Nowadays, we know that environmental problems in the world are worrying many people, and this is undoubtedly the main problem of young people in modern life. Through this lesson, all students received the necessary information and gained a lot of knowledge and skills about preserving nature and reducing factors that can cause harm in the future.

Xulosa

“Environmental problems and True, False, Not Given questions in Reading” mavzusidagi dars zamonaviy pedagogik talablar asosida tashkil etilib, unda raqamli texnologiyalar va interfaol metodlardan samarali foydalanildi. Dars jarayonida elektron doska, slaydlar, interfaol o‘yinlar hamda guruhli ishlash usullari qo‘llanilishi o‘quvchilarning darsga bo‘lgan qiziqishini oshirib, ularning faolligini ta‘minladi. True, False, Not Given savol turlarini o‘rgatishda qo‘llanilgan amaliy yondashuvlar o‘quvchilarning matni tahlil qilish, kalit so‘zlarni aniqlash, mantiqiy xulosa chiqarish kabi muhim ko‘nikmalarini rivojlantirishga xizmat qildi. Shuningdek, role play va speaking mashg‘ulotlari orqali o‘quvchilarning og‘zaki nutqi, mustaqil fikrlashi va kommunikativ kompetensiyasi shakllandi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar.

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